

Dual-Band Piecewise-Linear Profile Feed-Horns for the Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer Mission

G. Addamo, *Member, IEEE*, G. Virone, *Senior Member, IEEE*, M. Lumia, B. Fiorelli, G. Dassano, Marco Grilli, and O.A. Peverini, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—This paper presents the design strategy and the experimental results on the Ku/Ka dual-band feed-horn developed within the Phase A/B1 study of the Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer, which is one of the new six Expansion missions of the European Copernicus flagship programme on Earth observation operating in five frequency channels. The radiometer requirements translate into a dense focal plane composed by compact and lightweight dual-band feed horns. The optimum illumination was derived in terms of Bloch waves and the applicability of piecewise-linear profile feed-horns for its synthesis in the case of two highly-separated Ku/Ka frequency bands (1:1.95) was investigated. The presented feed-horn design was validated up to a technological readiness level of 6. The reported performances at antenna level for the complete Ku/Ka-band feed cluster demonstrate the feasibility of dual-band smooth-wall feed-horns focal-planes meeting all the Earth observation requirements in terms of footprints, beam- and wide-beam efficiencies, and cross-polarization.

Index Terms—Dual-band antennas, horn antennas, Earth observing systems, radiometers

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer (CIMR) Mission is one of the six Copernicus Expansion Missions, an Earth monitoring initiative led by the European Union (EU) and carried out in partnership with the EU Member States and the European Space Agency (ESA). The primary objectives of CIMR are the estimate of the sea ice concentration and extent, and of the sea surface temperature, with very small spatial resolution and high accuracy [1].

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G. Addamo, G. Virone, M. Lumia, and, O. A. Peverini are with the Istituto di Elettronica e di Ingegneria dell'Informazione e delle Telecomunicazioni, National Research Council of Italy, 10129 Turin, Italy (e-mail: giuseppe.addamo@ieit.cnr.it).

B. Fiorelli is with the Antenna and Sub-Millimetre Waves Section, European Space Agency, 2200 Noordwijk, Netherlands (e-mail: benedetta.fiorelli@esa.int).

Marco Grilli is with OHB-Italia, Via Gallarate 150, 20151 Milan, Italy (e-mail: marco.grilli@ohb-italia.it).

G. Dassano is with Dipartimento di Elettronica e Telecomunicazioni, Politecnico di Torino, 10129 Turin, Italy (e-mail: gianluca.dassano@polito.it). Color versions of one or more of the figures in this paper are available online at <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>.

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CIMR is a conical scanning radiometer, such as its precursors AMSR-E [2], SMAP [3], and MWI [4]. The Observation Zenith Angle (OZA), which is the angle between the satellite viewing direction and the local zenith on Earth, can range from 53.5° to 56.5°. The on-ground footprint size shall be lower than 60 km, 15 km, 15 km, 5.5 km and 4 km in the L (1.413 GHz ± 14 MHz), C (6.925 GHz ± 412 MHz), X (10.65 GHz ± 50 MHz), Ku (18.7 GHz ± 100 MHz) and Ka (36.5 GHz ± 500 MHz) bands. The footprint size is defined as the arithmetic mean of the two principal axes of the ellipse corresponding to the intersection of each individual beam at half the maximum power level with the Earth's surface represented by the WGS-84 ellipsoid. For each channel, the antenna sub-system shall guarantee beam (BE) and wide-beam efficiencies (WBE) better than 93 % and 96 %. These parameters correspond to the percentage of integrated antenna pattern in the angular region within 2.5 and 3 times the footprint, respectively [5]. They define the systematic errors on the measured brightness temperatures induced by regions far from the footprint, whose residual knowledge uncertainty contribute to the total radiometric uncertainty at L1B level [5]. The cross-polarization pattern integrated over 3 times the footprint angular region shall be lower than 2%. This figure of merit will be referred in the following as instrument cross-polarization.

The CIMR antenna sub-system design (end of phase A) is summarized in section II.A, where the requirements for the Ku/Ka feed-horn design are also derived using a Bloch-wave approach. This is particularly convenient, since it assures that the defined feed-horn radiation patterns can be obtained by superposition of circular waveguide modes. The dual-band horn design strategy and its final geometry are discussed in section II.B. The experimental results and their impact on the performance at antenna level for the Ku/Ka-band CIMR feed cluster are finally reported in section III.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

A. CIMR Antenna Sub-System

The design of the CIMR conically-scanning instrument considered in this work is based on an antenna subsystem rotating at 6.5 r.p.m. with a mesh off-axis parabolic reflector with a diameter of 8 m, $f/D = 1$, and clearance equal to 4.56 m (data corresponding to the end of the study phase A). The on-board view angle is 47.075°. The reflector is illuminated by the cluster of antenna-feeds arranged according to the focal-

Fig. 1. CIMR focal-plane considered in this work (phase A)

plane of Fig. 1 and operating as single-feed-per-beam. The antenna-feed cluster was defined in order to comply with the coverage requirements in terms of *i*) footprints, beam and wide-beam efficiencies, instrument cross-polarization *ii*) complete on-ground coverage (*i.e.*, required overlap between adjacent footprints of the same channel), *iii*) no hole at the pole (*i.e.*, required minimum OZAs to grant full coverage of the pole area from the satellite orbit), while being subjected to mechanical, thermal, and interface constraints.

In the present focal-plane cluster, the Ku and Ka bands share the same antenna-feed chains in order to minimize the mass, while satisfying the antenna requirements. The same solution was selected for the C- and X-band channels. The resulting configuration consists in ten dual-linear polarization Ku/Ka-band and four dual-linear polarization C/X-band antenna-feed chains. The L-band channel will be instead implemented through an aperture array of Ruag elements [6].

For each channel, the optimum illumination of the reflector (to achieve the required footprint and beam efficiencies) was derived exploiting a HE_{11} -like model based on the Bloch wave that provides minimum feed cross-polarization as described in [7]. This approach was preferred with respect to a Gaussian or a classical HE_{11} model, because the Bloch wave is naturally described as a particular combination of circular-waveguide modes. A symmetric corrugation in circular waveguide of diameter D with height h and width w equal to $\lambda/4$ and $\lambda/7$, respectively, has been considered as unit cell. The period p is equal to $\lambda/4$ where λ is the free-space wavelength at the central frequency of the channel. Therefore, for the Ku band: $h=p=4$ mm, $w=2.3$ mm; for the Ka band: $h=p=2.05$ mm, $w=1.17$ mm. For each channel, the optimum illumination was obtained by parametric analyses versus the aperture diameter D . The feed-horn apertures for the Ku- and Ka-band channels are approximately 64.24 mm and 52 mm, respectively, for which the optimum radiation patterns are shown in Fig. 2. Their modal content is similar to a Potter horn with 86% of TE_{11} and 13% of TM_{11} and low contribution (around 1%) of higher order modes (specifically TM_{12} and TM_{13}). In Ka-band the reflector is illuminated by the main lobe and the first side-lobe, which is in counter phase, in order to achieve the performances required at secondary level *i.e.* similar footprint for Ku and Ka despite the band separation (1:1.95). The optimum C and X illumination presents similar patterns.

Fig. 2. Comparison between the simulated radiation patterns in the 45-degree plane of the final Ku/Ka-band feed-horn geometry and of the Block-wave model. The vertical dashed line indicates the illumination angle of the reflector $\theta_0 = 22.2$ deg.

B. The Ku/Ka-band Feed-Horn design

The implementation of the focal plane of Fig. 1 is strictly related to the problem of synthesizing two sets of modal distributions on the same feed-horn aperture. Since the frequency separation of the Ku/Ka band is larger than the C/X one (1:1.95 versus 1:1.59), the synthesis of the Ku/Ka-band feed-horn was considered as a suitable benchmark.

Among the possible feed-horn configurations, including corrugated [7]-[10], choked [11], and spline/piecewise-linear [12]-[16] architectures, the latter was selected for electromagnetic and mechanical reasons. Indeed, this architecture provides the degrees of freedoms necessary to synthesize the desired radiation patterns, while being a compact and lightweight solution compatible also with 3D printing technologies [15]. This architecture was initially introduced for implementing high-efficiency feed-horns in multi-beam antenna subsystems for high/very-high throughput communication satellites [13], [14]. Then its applicability to radio-astronomy and astrophysics receivers was also investigated [12], [16]. To the best of the Authors' knowledge, this is the first study reporting on dual-band piecewise-linear feed-horns meeting all the EO requirements in terms of footprints, beam- and wide-beam efficiencies, and cross-polarization.

The feed-horn geometry was synthesized in three steps.

At first, the design of two single-band feed-horns for the Ku- and Ka-band channels, respectively, was carried out with the goal of synthesizing the optimum radiation patterns defined by the Block-wave models, while minimizing the cross-polarization and guaranteeing a high return loss (better than 30 dB). The two feed-horn designs share the same input-port diameter (9.86 mm) and aperture diameter (64.24 mm). The former was selected to guarantee the mono-modal condition in both Ku and Ka bands. The latter, instead, is the aperture diameter of the optimum Block-wave model in Ku band. A flare angle of 7 degree was exploited as a good compromise between length and input reflection coefficient. The geometry of each single-band feed-horn was derived by optimizing through a conjugate gradient technique the radial and longitudinal coordinates of the piecewise-linear profile nodes, as described in [15]. The analyses were carried out by using a software based on the Coupled Integral-Equation

Fig. 3. Geometry of the Ku/Ka piecewise-linear feed-horn (solid black line) compared to the single-band configurations (red: Ku-, green: Ka-

Technique (CIET) [17]. According to the channel bandwidths of 1.7% in Ku band and 2.8% in Ka band, 7 and 9 nodes were necessary to achieve the required performances. The corresponding profiles are shown in Fig. 3 with red (Ku-band) and green (Ka-band) dashed lines. The Ka-band feed-horn layout is longer than the Ku-band one, since the horn aperture was set to the optimum value for the Ku band.

Then, a homotopic transformation (with homotopic parameter $\eta = 0.65$) between the two single-band optimum profiles was applied in order to define a guess geometry for the optimization of the dual-band feed-horn. The radiation patterns of the single-band Block-wave models were considered in the goal function by minimizing the difference between the desired and realized radiation patterns up to 40 degrees in the principal and diagonal axes (*i.e.*, $\varphi = 0^{\circ}, 45^{\circ}$ and 90°). At this stage, 20 nodes were considered to provide sufficient degrees of freedom in the optimization process. Since the two single-band feed-horns had different longitudinal lengths, the profile slopes were allowed to assume both positive and negative values.

Finally, the geometry was further refined by considering the feed-horn illuminating the reflector and optimizing the CIMR antenna performance at secondary level. This design phase was carried out through a closed-loop simulation tool based on the integration of the CIET software (for the feed-horn analysis) with the GRASP software [18] (for the PO-PTD analysis of the reflector). In this step, the optimum horn phase-center position is also found. One of the main advantages of the described procedure is that the combined analysis (*i.e.*, feed-horn illuminating the reflector), which is the most time-consuming task, was applied only in the last refinement step. Figure 2 shows the comparison between the radiation patterns of the final feed-horn geometry and the reference Block-wave model in the 45-deg plane, in which the maximum cross-polarization levels are radiated. The performance of the final geometry agrees with the requirements derived in II.A.

The final feed-horn geometry is shown in Fig. 3 (solid black line). As it can be expected, the final profile shares features from both single-band designs. At low values of z , the optimized profile resembles the Ka-band one (green) with a Potter-like fashion, whereas a convergence to the Ku-band profile (red) is visible towards the aperture. The nodal points of the final design in Fig. 3 (black solid line) are $z_i = \{0, 9.391, 21.416, 23.603, 25.061, 27.388, 29.277, 36.090, 59.436, 79.648, 96.005, 111.517, 156.758, 167.108, 190.116, 193.723, 217.703, 219.091, 220.528, 222.528\}$ mm and $y_i = \{4.930, 4.946, 5.377$

Fig. 4. Ku/Ka-band feed-horn prototype under test.

6.144 6.927 6.978 7.239 11.912 11.965 13.364 14.292 16.575 24.608 26.076 26.641 27.701 30.050 31.271 32.120 32.120} mm. The phase center is -8 mm behind the horn aperture.

A worst-case sensitivity analysis was performed considering one thousand realizations affected by random errors of ± 0.1 mm over all the geometrical parameters. It has to be remarked that typical manufacturing errors for standard machining technologies are lower than 0.04 mm for this kind of parts. The resulting mean values and the standard deviations for the main electromagnetic performances of the feed-horn are compared to the nominal values in Table I. These results demonstrate the robustness of the developed solution with respect to manufacturing uncertainties.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The Ku/Ka-band feed-horn was manufactured in aluminum 6000-series alloy through turning (preliminary coarse manufacturing), and electrical-discharge machining (final fine manufacturing). The dimensional accuracy is within 0.02 mm and the surface roughness is lower than 1 μm . The minimum thickness of the metal walls is 2.5 mm with reinforcement in the region of the input circular-waveguide port in order to enhance stability during manufacturing. The SurTec650 surface-treatment was applied to the prototype. The weight of the feed-horn is approximately 200 g and the component fits within a cylinder of 72.4 mm (diameter) x 232.5 mm (length). The prototype was tested in anechoic chamber (see Fig. 4) through a far-field setup equipped with a three-axes motor and control systems that provide a positioning accuracy of 0.025 deg and the possibility of aligning the phase center of the AUT with the mechanical center of the positioner. The Tx/Rx system consists of a network analyzer configured with an IF bandwidth of 100 Hz in order to maximize the dynamic range. Figures 5(a)-(d) show the comparison between the simulated and measured reflection coefficients and maximum cross-polarization levels for the Ku and Ka channels. The measured insertion losses in Ku and Ka band are 0.07 ± 0.03 dB and 0.04 ± 0.03 dB, being 0.03 dB the measurement uncertainty. The measured antenna gains are approximately 20.4 dB and 24.4 dB in Ku and Ka band, respectively. Figures 5(e)-(f) report the comparison between the measured and the simulated co- and cross-polar radiation patterns at 18.7 GHz and 35.5 GHz in the 45-deg plane. The good agreement between measurement and simulation confirms the validity of the design and its high performance. The CIMR antenna-level performance at Ku/Ka-band was computed using the measured radiation patterns of the feed-horn prototype as inputs in the

GRASP software. Table II reports the minimum, mean and maximum values over the ten focal-plane positions (see Fig. 1) and over frequency for the main antenna parameters. The achieved range has been considered acceptable at the end of the phase A/B1.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The capability of piecewise-linear feed-horns to synthesize the optimum radiation patterns for the CIMR reflector even considering highly-separated frequency bands (1:1.95) has

been demonstrated in this paper. Therefore, this architecture can be considered as a good candidate for the antenna subsystem of the next Phases B2/C/D/E of the mission and for future Earth Observation multi-band payloads.

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Fig. 5. Comparison between the measured and simulated performances of the Ku/Ka-band feed-horn prototype. (a) Reflection coefficient S_{11} in Ku band. (b) Reflection coefficient S_{11} in Ka band. (c) Maximum radiated cross-polarization X-pol in Ku band. (d) Maximum radiated cross-polarization X-pol in Ka band. (e) Co- and cross-polar radiation patterns in the 45-degree plane at 18.7 GHz. (f) Co- and cross-polar radiation patterns in the 45-degree plane at 36.5 GHz.

TABLE I
DESIGN ELECTROMAGNETIC PERFORMANCES AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE KU/KA-BAND FEED-HORN

Parameter	Nominal value (dB)	Mean value (dB)	Standard deviation (dB)
Max S_{11} in Ku band	-32.8	-31.7	1.30
Max S_{11} in Ka band	-44.2	-44.5	1.40
Max X-pol. in Ku band	-32.5	-32.8	0.71
Max X-pol. in Ka band	-29.0	-29.8	0.85
Taper at θ_0 in Ku band	-22.2	-22.2	0.23
Taper at θ_0 in Ka band	-32.5	-32.6	0.50

$\theta_0 = 22.2$ deg is the illumination angle of the reflector. The mean value and the standard deviation refer to manufacturing uncertainties of 0.1 mm.

TABLE II
ANTENNA PERFORMANCES AT SECONDARY LEVEL OF THE KU- AND KA-BAND CHANNELS

Parameter	Min Value	Mean value	Max value
Footprint in Ku band (km)	4.8	5.3	5.9
Footprint in Ka band (km)	3.6	4.1	4.4
Beam efficiency in Ku band (%)	93.3	95.1	97.1
Beam efficiency in Ka band (%)	94.4	95.9	98.7
Wide-beam efficiency in Ku band (%)	96.6	97.3	98.0
Wide-beam efficiency in Ka band (%)	97.7	98.3	99.2
Integrated cross-pol. in Ku band (%)	0.26	0.32	0.37
Integrated cross-pol. in Ka band (%)	0.20	0.27	0.36

The results correspond to the Ku/Ka-band antenna-feed cluster of Fig. 1, when the measured radiation patterns of the prototype are considered in the secondary-level antenna simulations.

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